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Innovative Climate-Control System to Extend Range of Electric Vehicles and Improve Comfort (XERIC)

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D5.8_WP5_EMH

Report about 1st Workshop

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Summary:

XERIC’s grant agreement states that several public workshops are to be organized throughout the project’s lifetime. The first event was organized on November 24, 2016, in Bologna, Italy. Indeed, Emily-Romagna is a key region for the automotive industry.

The event was called **Improving Energy Efficiency in Electric Vehicles**, with *Insights on H2020 Initiatives on Energy Management* as a subtitle.

Following the recommendations received from the INEA agency, it was decided as soon as November 2015 to start clustering with other closely related EU projects in order to increase efficiency and impact through synergy. JOSPEL and OPTEMUS issued from the same Call on Green Vehicles have agreed to join forces. This first XERIC event was thus a joint event. XERIC kept the lead to supervise the event organization, with ASTER (Emily-Romagna high tech network) being a subcontractor to take care of the logistics of the event and of communication in Italy.

This document explains how the event was advertised and to whom, and who participated. The document details practical organization, programme, communication and audience.

With about 100 attendees, 15 oral presentations and a very active B2B session, the event has been really a great success as testified by satisfaction survey realized afterwards.

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1. Background information

1.1. Context

XERIC's grant agreement states that several public workshops are to be organized throughout the project's lifetime. Organizing events falls within WP5. The European Membrane House (EMH) is the leader of WP5.

The grant agreement also states that the first event was to be organized in Bologna, Italy, since Emily-Romagna is a key region for the automotive industry, and that ASTER (Emily-Romagna high tech network) would be a subcontractor taking care of the logistics of the event.

It was decided to **start clustering** as early as possible. The JOSPEL and OPTEMUS European Projects agreed to join forces: this first XERIC event was thus a joint event. JOSPEL and OPTEMUS are also receiving funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program. They too are taking up the challenge of improving the operating range of electric vehicles.

XERIC via EMH (in the person of Guylène Soula, communication officer) kept the lead for supervising the event's organization and ensuring joint communication actions to promote the event.

1.2. Choice of title for the event

A title encompassing enough to cover the 3 projects was needed: *Improving Energy Management in Electric Vehicles* served that purpose.

Laying emphasis on H2020 was thought to be a strong incentive for people to attend the event. Hence the choice of having the following subtitle to the event: *Insights on H2020 Initiatives on Energy Management*.

1.3. Event's purpose

The purpose of the event was to:

- Disseminate-share what the XERIC, OPTEMUS, JOSPEL projects are doing;
- Inform about key expertise the project's participants have;
- Disseminate and share what the European Commission is doing for electric mobility;
- Offer networking opportunities:
 - a) Have the 38 partners from the 3 projects discover each other's expertise;
 - b) Have **external participants** discover the 38 partners and *vice-versa*.

1.4. Online registration

All registrations were done online. Online registrations opened on July 29th and closed on November 18th.

2. Programme committee, logistics, overall coordination

2.1. Programme committee

The XERIC's partners drafted the guidelines for the day during XERIC's 3rd Progress meeting in May 2016. The JOSPEL and OPTEMUS projects were then asked to provide input: they suggested titles and themes of talks that could be presented during the workshop.

A programme committee made up of 4 XERIC partners then made the final decisions to decide on a final agenda for the day, on the basis of the input received from the other two projects.

2.2. Logistics

November 24, 2016 was chosen as a date not conflicting with other local events in Bologna nor with other events devoted to Electric Vehicles elsewhere.

MAST was selected as a venue answering the needs for the event (conference room, cafeteria and in-house caterer ...).

ASTER (Emily-Romagna high tech network) acted as a subcontractor to the XERIC project to take care of the logistics of the event and of communication in Italy. ASTER took care of hiring the conference hall, dealing with the caterer, having the communication material printed, etc.

2.3. Overall coordination

The overall coordination of the event was taken care of by an EMH staff member (Guylène Soula , Communication Officer). EMH took care of setting up a joint communication plan to be used by the 3 different projects. EMH liaised with each of the three projects to keep them abreast of the set-up of the event. EMH liaised with the subcontractor ASTER for all things taken care of by ASTER.

3. Programme

The idea of parallel sessions was ruled out: the idea was to have people stick together to create a strong clustering impetus. The day was thus split into two distinct parts: talks on the one hand, and bilateral meetings on the other.

Lamberto Salvan from JOSPEL kindly said yes to be Master of Ceremony for the day.

3.1. Talks

It was decided to have:

- general presentations of XERIC, JOSPEL and OPTEMUS, the idea being to say as much as possible without infringing on confidentiality;
- more technical talks highlighting aspects specific to each of the three projects;
- talks taken care of by the members of XERIC's Strategic Advisory Board, the idea being to take advantage of the presence of recognized experts in the fields of automotive industry, intensification of processes and systems and development of high-tech products such as membranes so as to provide new relevant information and open new perspectives on the subjects at heart of the three projects.

3.2. B2B meetings

Bilateral meetings are a quick, easy and efficient way to meet new cooperation partners. 68 participants booked meetings. It made up a total of **31** bilateral meetings.

The following chart was developed based on the responses received following the completion of a satisfaction questionnaire. This pattern shows that while about one-third of scheduled meetings have not been held for different reasons, the Satisfaction Index on those that actually took place is very high: 27% new co-operations envisaged; 34% new contacts announced ; for about 23% of participants the feeling that the exercise had been very informative !

3.3. Demonstrations

A possibility was offered to participants to bring demos. Four participants (CTAG - Automotive Technology Centre of Galicia; Universidad EAFIT, Medellin, Colombia;

Fraunhofer ITWM; DENSO AUTOMOTIVE Deutschland GmbH) brought demonstrations and had the opportunity to present them during a specific timeslot.

3.4. Posters

Another possibility was for participants to bring posters: four participants seized the opportunity (Fraunhofer ITWM; Bloomfield s.r.l.; KAITEK s.r.l; Piaggio & C. SpA; Universidad EAFIT, Medellin, Colombia)

The full programme is available in Appendix 1.

4. Communication

4.1. Dedicated website for the event

A website dedicated to the event was set up. The Enterprise Europe Network (EEN) software was used since it matched the needs for the event: it combines a “usual” website, a registration form and registration/profile creation for **B2Bs (“b2match platform”)**. ASTER is part of EEN: this is how we were able to use this software.

It was fully personalized to display the visual identity of the event.

Here’s a screenprint of the top of the homepage:

The screenshot shows the homepage of the event website. The main header features the title "IMPROVING Energy Efficiency IN ELECTRIC VEHICLES" and the date "24 November 2016 - Bologna, Italy". Below the header is a navigation menu with links for Home, Participants, About us, Programme, Speakers, Registration, Practical information, and Contact. The main content area includes a registration status box indicating that registration closed on 18 Nov 2016, a list of organizers (ERIC and ASTER), a schedule table, and a list of participants by country.

Improving energy efficiency in electric vehicles

Increasing the range of electric vehicles remains one of the biggest challenges in the automotive industry. As a result, 38 partners from 3 EU-funded projects organise a one-day event to share their insights on the latest trends and technologies to improve energy efficiency in electric vehicles. Download the presentations!

REGISTRATION IS NOW OPEN!

Come meet with a European mix of specialists in Electric Vehicles (EVs) who are excited about taking up the challenge of EVs range and broadening the market of EVs! Click on the "Register" button to start filling the online registration form.

Why you should attend

You're in R&D/industry/you're an end-user and you're related to electric vehicles?

This one-day event is meant for you:

- You'll learn what the **European Commission** is doing for electric mobility;
- You'll get a unique insight into the latest research and development on energy management in electric vehicles - thanks to our key-note speakers;

REGISTRATION
closed since 18 Nov 2016

ORGANISERS

SCHEDULE

Registration	31 Jul - 18 Nov
Meeting Selection	1 Aug - 23 Nov
Event	24 Nov

DETAILS

Language	English
Costs	Free of charge
Venue	MAST Gallery, Bologna

BILATERAL MEETINGS

Participants	68
Meetings	43

PARTICIPANTS

Austria	1
Belgium	1
Bosnia-Herzegovina	1
Denmark	3

Furthermore, announcements about the event were posted on the XERIC, JOSPEL and OPTEMUS websites.

4.2. Teasers

The event was announced twice in XERIC's newsletters:

- as a "Save the Date" in XERIC's 1st Newsletter issued in December 2015:

One-day Event for Electric Mobility in Bologna

Save the date! XERIC will be organising a one-day event devoted to **electric mobility** in November 2016 in Bologna, Italy.

The more, the merrier: the JOSPEL and OPTEMUS projects said yes to contributing to the event. Information about programme, venue and registration will be regularly posted on XERIC's website.

ASTER, Emilia-Romagna's High-Tech Network, will provide its know-how to make a success of this event.

- as "Grow your Network!" in XERIC's 2nd Newsletter issued in May 2016:

One-day event: Improving Energy Efficiency in EVs

Grow your network!

Increasing the **range of electric vehicles** remains one of the biggest challenges in the automotive industry. As a result, XERIC and 2 other EU-funded projects have decided to organise a one-day event on the latest trends and technologies to improve energy efficiency in electric vehicles.

You're from R&D or Industry, or maybe you're an end user? Join us on **November 24** in **Bologna, Italy**:

- you'll learn what the European Commission is doing for electric mobility;
- you'll get a unique insight into the latest research and development on energy management in electric vehicles;
- you'll establish new contacts for collaborations thanks to bilateral meetings that you'll have pre-booked online.

Access to the event is FREE if you register.

Online registration will start in June on a dedicated website: you'll receive an email when registration opens.

If you have any questions or need more information, don't hesitate to get in touch with our Communication Officer, *Guyène Soula*, at guyene.soula@univ-montp2.fr.

In Italy, ASTER carried out the following communication actions:

- The event was promoted 6 times (from August to November) *via* ASTER's Newsletter reaching almost 18.000 people;
- The event was promoted *via* the Italian and the English version of the ASTER's website;
- The event was also promoted *via* the Emilia-Romagna Region's website.

4.3. Email announcements

Information about the event was disseminated *via* email to reach a maximum number of potential participants.

Three emails were sent: on July 29th, on September 16th, on October 20th.

For each announcement, EMH took care of devising and sending a single announcement email for all the structures involved (ASTER, XERIC, JOSPEL and OPTEMUS) to communicate about the event. The communication people from INSERO, one of the partner of JOSPEL, kindly proof-read the announcements and made suggestions to improve them.

For confidentiality reasons, ASTER, XERIC and JOSPEL were in charge of sending the announcements to their own lists.

4.4. Communication lists for email announcements

ASTER started with a list of about 115 persons in Italy and expanded it. XERIC started with a list with about 125 names and expanded it.

EMH asked JOSPEL and OPTEMUS to draw their own communication lists.

EMH got in touch with 30 other EU-funded projects working on the theme of electric vehicles.

A targeted audience was also reached in Spain via SERNAUTO, thanks to AIN (one of XERIC's partners). SERNAUTO is the Spanish Association of Equipment Manufacturers and Automotive Components. They are in charge of the Spanish Technological Platform of Automotive and Sustainability.

EMH also got in touch with the Automobile Club of France.

Communication lists were thus expanded and the last electronic announcement was sent to **267 email addresses** (several of these addresses being aliases, thus reaching more than one person only).

4.5. On-site signage

The participants were welcomed at the venue's main entrance by a big flag displaying the graphic identity of the event. Roll-ups were on view at the reception desk, in the conference room and in the cafeteria.

Big flag at the venue's main entrance

Roll up at reception desk

4.6. Video

A professional video-maker was hired by ASTER. A 3-mn video covering the event was made.

Here's the text introducing the video:

Improving Energy Efficiency in Electric Vehicles | Bologna, November 24, 2016

This was a joint event organised by the XERIC, JOSPEL and OPTEMUS European projects. All 3 projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and are taking up the challenge of improving the operating range of electric vehicles.

Click on the video to discover images of the event and hear what the people involved in the projects say about the challenges and opportunities they are facing. You'll also hear their view on the future of electric vehicles and the added value of organising such a joint event.

www.xeric.eu

Click here to view the video:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kMQpooZyhTs&feature=youtu.be>

4.7. Memory of the event

A webpage specifically dedicated to the event has been created on XERIC's public website. It will remain available at :

<http://xeric.eu/improving-energy-efficiency-in-electric-vehicles-one-day-event/>

This page features the video made, the programme, the list of participants and a pdf document with pictures of the event.

The speakers' presentations can also be downloaded from this page.

5. Audience

5.1. Audience targeted

SMEs, companies, research labs, technology centers, from Europe were the main target, SMEs, companies, research labs, technology centers from elsewhere were welcome too but not directly targeted.

5.2. Actual number of participants

Our rough estimation of the number of participants was 80 / 90 participants.

100 persons have registered to the event, out of which **92 showed up**.

Here's where the participants come from, on the basis of the registration forms:

PARTICIPANTS		
	Austria	1
	Belgium	1
	Bosnia-Herzegovina	1
	Denmark	3
	France	6
	Germany	8
	Italy	58
	Luxembourg	2
	Portugal	2
	Spain	14
	United Kingdom	4
Total		100

The list of participants is available in Appendix 2.

6. Budget

What	Cost
Personnel	7 200,00
Conference hall and tour	5 000,00
Catering (welcome coffee, coffee breaks and lunch)	4 000,00
Video	1 000,00
Communication and promotional material (including photographer and EEN software for websites)	5 000, 00
Total	22 200,00

The event was free of charge for the participants (no registration fees).

On the eve of the workshop, an informal networking dinner was organised. With the exception the XERIC's SAB members and the joint Project Officer of the three project who were invited by XERIC, all the others paid on their own project's budget.

7. Satisfaction Survey

39 persons answered the satisfaction survey. The questions asked for this satisfaction survey are displayed in Appendix 3.

It is clear from the analysis of the first two diagrams presented above that, on the one hand, the general organization of the workshop has been fully appreciated by the participants (more than 95% positive answers) and that 75% of the attendants have considered the presentations as pertinent.

Assistance before and during the event

Website

Location

The levels of satisfaction for the assistance before and during the event, regarding the website specifically dedicated to the workshop and the location -MAST- are close to 100 %.

Other answers received concerning the welcome dinner testify that it was highly appreciated for informal contacts and clustering spirit it allowed.

As a whole, a great event!

Appendices

Appendix 1: Programme

Appendix 2: List of participants

Appendix 3: Satisfaction survey: questions asked

Appendix 4: Pictures of the event